

Osmose Calibration Guidelines

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Table of contents

1	Introduction	4
2	Package Install	5
2.1	Free-Knot Splines	5
2.2	Empirical selectivity	5
2.3	Calibrar	6
3	Calibrar description	7
3.1	General structure of <code>calibrar</code>	7
3.2	Calibration info	7
3.3	Observed data	9
3.4	Simulated data	11
4	Initialization of the model	12
4.1	Inputs needed for the initialization	12
4.2	Model initialization	15
5	Calibration	20
5.1	Calibration set-up	20
6	References	25

List of Figures

3.1	Diagram representing the functioning of the calibrar package (adapted from Oliveros-Ramos and Shin 2016). The grey area groups the outputs produced by the package (the objective function and the optimal parameters of the model). Rectangles with broken border lines show user inputs which are needed to configurate the optimization. Rounded rectangles show main package functions. . . .	8
4.1	Diagram showing the initialization steps	19

List of Tables

3.1	Calibration informations	8
3.2	Example of calibration biomass data	10
3.3	Example of calibration yield data	10
3.4	Example of calibration catch-at-length data	11
5.1	Original calibration settings	23
5.2	Corrected calibration settings	23

Chapter 1

Introduction

The aim of the present document is to introduce the interannual calibration of an OSMOSE configuration ([OSMOSE Peru](#)) configuration using the [calibrar](#) package.

Section [2](#) describes the packages that need to be installed to run the calibration. Section [3](#) describes the general functioning of `calibrar` (largely inspired from [Leforestier \(2019\)](#)). The last two sections describe the R tools used to facilitate the set-up of Osmose calibration. Section [4](#) describes the Osmose initialization method used to initialize the model prior to calibration. Finally, Section [5](#) describes the functions used to initialize the calibration itself.

Chapter 2

Package Install

To run the calibration, the following packages need to be installed manually.

2.1 Free-Knot Splines

The `fks` package provides algorithms for fitting free-knot splines for data with one independent variable and one dependent variable. Four free-knot spline algorithms are provided for the case where the number of knots is known in advance. A knot-search algorithm is provided for the case where the number of knots is not known in advance. In addition, methods are available to compute the fitted values, the residuals, and the coefficients of the splines, and to plot the results, along with a method to summarize the results. This package is used to estimate a flexible selectivity by the `empirical.selectivity` package described in the next section.

This package must be installed from [Ricardo Oliveros-Ramos's fork](#):

```
library("devtools")
install_github("roliveros-ramos/fks")
```

2.2 Empirical selectivity

The `empirical.selectivity` (<https://github.com/roliveros-ramos/empirical.selectivity/>) package contains empirical selectivity fitting and diagnostics functions. This package is used to estimate the fishing selectivity during the OSMOSE initialization process when catch-at-length is provided.

This package must be installed from [Ricardo Oliveros-Ramos's fork](#):

```
library("devtools")
install_github("roliveros-ramos/empirical.selectivity")
```

2.3 Calibrar

The `calibrar` package (<https://github.com/roliveros-ramos/calibrar/>) allows the parameter estimation or calibration of complex models, including stochastic ones. It is a generic tool that can be used for fitting any type of models, especially those with non-differentiable objective functions (Oliveros-Ramos and Shin 2016). It supports multiple phases and constrained optimization. It implements maximum likelihood estimation methods and automated construction of the objective function from simulated model outputs. This is the package that is currently used for the calibration of OSMOSE.

The `calibrar` package must be installed from the `drat` OSMOSE repository (and not its CRAN version):

```
library("devtools")
install.packages("calibrar", repo="https://osmose-model.github.io/drat/")
```

The `drat` OSMOSE repository will always contains the latest tested version functional for OSMOSE calibration.

Chapter 3

Calibrar description

In this chapter, the R package `calibrar` is described, based on Oliveros-Ramos and Shin (2016).

3.1 General structure of `calibrar`

The general structure of the `calibrar` workflow is shown in Figure 3.1.

The main function of the package is `calibrate()`, which performs minimization of the objective function. The two compulsory arguments (i.e. without default settings) of `calibrate()` are the starting search points (`par`) argument and the function to minimize (`fn`).

The user can give a vector of values as initial parameters if he has already an idea of the values of the parameters. In that case, the initial exploration will be done following a normal distribution around the starting points given.

The function to minimize `fn` results from `createObjectiveFunction()` that combines the observed and simulated data, according to calibration information coming from a csv file read by `getCalibrationInfo()`, as discussed below.

3.2 Calibration info

Calibration informations must be provided on a CSV file that contains informations about the data that will be used in the calibration process (see Table 3.1). This file will be read by the `getCalibrationInfo()` function of the `calibrar` package.

The table columns are:

- `variable` is the list of the variables that will be fit the model with observations.

Figure 3.1: Diagram representing the functioning of the calibrar package (adapted from Oliveros-Ramos and Shin 2016). The grey area groups the outputs produced by the package (the objective function and the optimal parameters of the model). Rectangles with broken border lines show user inputs which are needed to configurate the optimization. Rounded rectangles show main package functions.

Table 3.1: Calibration informations

variable	type	calibrate	cv	use_data	file	varid	nrows
biomass.anchoveta	lnorm3	TRUE	0.25	TRUE	peru_biomass-index_month.csv	anchoveta	NA
biomass.merluza	lnorm3	TRUE	0.25	TRUE	peru_biomass-index_month.csv	merluza	NA
biomass.sardina	lnorm3	TRUE	0.25	TRUE	peru_biomass-index_month.csv	sardina	NA
biomass.jurel	lnorm3	TRUE	0.25	TRUE	peru_biomass-index_month.csv	jurel	NA
biomass.caballa	lnorm3	TRUE	0.25	TRUE	peru_biomass-index_month.csv	caballa	NA
biomass.mesopelagicos	lnorm3	TRUE	0.25	TRUE	peru_biomass-index_month.csv	mesopelagicos	NA
biomass.munida	lnorm3	TRUE	0.25	TRUE	peru_biomass-index_month.csv	munida	NA
biomass.pota	lnorm3	TRUE	0.25	TRUE	peru_biomass-index_month.csv	pota	NA
biomass.euphausidos	lnorm3	TRUE	0.25	TRUE	peru_biomass-index_month.csv	euphausidos	NA
yield.anchoveta	lnorm2	TRUE	0.05	TRUE	peru_yield_month.csv	anchoveta	NA

- `type` is the objective function that will be used in the fitting. It can either be a native function of the `calibrar` package or a user defined function.
- `calibrate` indicates whether the data is used in the calibration.
- `weights` provides the relative weights used to combine the partial objective values obtained for each variable.
- `useData` indicates whether data are read from the disk. If `useData=FALSE`, the observed value is set to `NULL` and the likelihood function is expected to use simulated data only. The latter option can be particularly useful to set penalties in the model outputs or parameters, where no observed data are needed.

The user can provide user-defined objective function instead of the ones provided in `calibrar`. These functions must be defined as follows:

```
user_rms <- function(obs, sim) {
  value = sqrt(sum((obs - sim)^2) / length(obs))
}
```

Warning:

If `useData = TRUE`, the name of the CSV file must be consistent with the name of the variable. For instance, if the variable is `PagellusErythrinus.thr`, the data file must be `PagellusErythrinus.thr.csv`

Warning:

The column names (i.e. the header) are important and must be as shown in Table 3.1

3.3 Observed data

The `getObservedData()` function gets back the observed data from csv files and transforms them into a list format. The data must be provided as CSV files. Biomass and yield data must be provided as shown in Table 3.2 and Table 3.3. They must have a `year` and a `month` columns, and one column for each species of the Osiose configuration considered. **Therefore, there is one file for all the species.**

Catch at length data must be formatted as shown on Table 3.4. In this case, **there with one file per species** and the columns correspond to the size-classes considered.

Table 3.2: Example of calibration biomass data

year	month	anchoveta	merluza	sardina	jurel	caballa	mesopelagicos	munida	pota	euphausidos
1992	1	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	0	NA	NA
1992	2	5209232	NA	1598172	2957578	696029	NA	0	NA	NA
1992	3	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	0	NA	NA
1992	4	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	0	NA	NA
1992	5	NA	209359	NA	NA	NA	NA	0	NA	NA
1992	6	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	0	NA	NA
1992	7	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	0	NA	NA
1992	8	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	0	NA	NA
1992	9	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	0	NA	NA
1992	10	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	0	NA	NA

Table 3.3: Example of calibration yield data

year	month	anchoveta	merluza	sardina	jurel	caballa	mesopelagicos	munida	pota	euphausidos
1992	1	431417	2201.388	268792	4776	2681	0	0	6088	0
1992	2	27150	2991.660	42826	5644	1774	0	0	5777	0
1992	3	4953	3130.991	175417	4680	999	0	0	2729	0
1992	4	359900	2603.076	105292	1822	406	0	0	2825	0
1992	5	798757	3473.512	88696	3207	507	0	0	3040	0
1992	6	423995	3096.366	92655	12353	389	0	0	9301	0
1992	7	204580	3353.622	162628	11855	252	0	0	12133	0
1992	8	77677	3056.693	113355	3168	114	0	0	11171	0
1992	9	8461	1382.376	46409	15899	29	0	0	20175	0
1992	10	163291	1693.858	77069	14460	141	0	0	14876	0

Table 3.4: Example of calibration catch-at-length data

year	month	X5	X5.5	X6	X6.5	X7	X7.5	X8	X8.5
1992	1	0	0	0	0.2911063	38.973432	157.525276	546.4288279	1336.838611
1992	2	0	0	0	0.0000000	0.769938	14.207316	78.0105038	231.245119
1992	3	0	0	0	0.0000000	0.000000	2.603748	23.4349406	91.137226
1992	4	0	0	0	0.0000000	0.000000	16.931032	130.8418019	532.173120
1992	5	0	0	0	0.0000000	1.468390	8.139969	83.8444090	226.610540
1992	6	0	0	0	0.0000000	0.000000	0.000000	1.1519410	36.426828
1992	7	0	0	0	0.0000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.0000000	0.639173
1992	8	0	0	0	0.0000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.0000000	0.000000
1992	9	0	0	0	0.0000000	0.000000	0.000000	0.0000000	0.000000
1992	10	0	0	0	0.0000000	0.000000	3.856299	0.6017496	11.317298

Note:

The CSV data separator must be ,

3.4 Simulated data

Simulated data are returned into a list format by `run_model()`, the second main function of the package that must be defined by the user. It must be defined as follows:

```
run_model = function(param, ...) {
  ...
}
```

The `param` argument is the list of the calibrated parameters, which is passed by the `calibrate` function.

The `run_model` function must achieve the following three tasks:

- write the set of parameters provided by `calibrate()` in a format the Osrose model is able to read
- launch the Osrose simulation from a command line with this set of parameters (by calling the `run_osrose` function of the Osrose package)
- get back the simulation outputs and return them after a transformation into a list format.

Chapter 4

Initialization of the model

Calibration of Osmose is a very slow process, since it implies running Osmose several times. These Osmose simulations must be long enough to reach equilibrium.

In order to improve the efficiency of the process, the Osmose package contains some tools that allow to initialize the Osmose model and therefore avoid the spin-up phase, thus saving some computation time.

In the following, this initialization phase is described.

4.1 Inputs needed for the initialization

In order to run the initialization, the user must provide, in an Osmose configuration file, some parameters that will be used in the process. In the `osmose-peru` case, these parameters are provided in the `osmose-peru_v4.x_develop/input/init_configuration.osm` file.

In the following section, the different parameters and data that can be used in the initialization process are described.

4.1.1 Duration of the egg stage

The duration of the egg stage is used internally to compute larval mortality and the gnomonic mortality (Caddy, John F. 1996). It has to be provided in days.

```
species.egg.stage.duration.sp0 = 2
```

4.1.2 Absolute biomass

The model used for the initialization is very simple and currently does not deal with the estimation of a catchability (scaling factor for abundance), so an estimate of absolute biomass in the full model domain is needed. When this information or a reasonable proxy is available, it can be provided as a time series that can also be used during the calibration process. If the information is not available, the best guesstimate available could be used instead, as a single value.

4.1.2.1 Absolute biomass time series

The observed biomass has to be provided in a csv file, similar in format to the ones provided as outputs in OSMOSE. A column with the exact name of the species X (spX) is required. It is possible to use just one file for all the species in the model, provided the column names match the species names. Additional columns (e.g. biomass of background species) are allowed. However, all the time series need to have the same frequency, i.e. the same number of time steps per year (use is consistent with the `ndtPerYear` in other parts of the model, like the `netCDF` forcing). A biomass cutoff size needs to be provided, to exclude the biomass of early life stages that is not included in the estimates of absolute biomass, and can be significant in magnitude.

```
observed.biomass.file.sp0 = ../../data/peru_biomass.acousticSurvey-index_month.csv
observed.biomass.ndtPerYear.sp0 = 12
observed.biomass.cutoff.size.sp0 = 5
```

4.1.2.2 Absolute biomass guesstimate

When the biomass guess is provided, it takes precedence to the time series. The cutoff still needs to be provided.

```
observed.biomass.guess.sp0 = 5000000
observed.biomass.cutoff.size.sp0 = 5
```

4.1.3 Landings

Fisheries landings by species for all the model domain need to be provided. If a species is targeted by multiple fisheries, the addition of all landings is what is needed as input. In this case, only time series are allowed.

```
fisheries.yield.file.sp0 = ../../data/peru_yield_month.csv
fisheries.yield.ndtPerYear.sp0 = 12
```

If the values in the time series of landings for a particular species are all equal to zero, the species is assumed to be non-harvested, and harvested in any other case.

4.1.4 Catch at length.

The model used for the initialization is size-based and needs catch-at-length data for every harvested species in order to compute the estimates of initial biomass. In this case, estimates of selectivity will also be computed. If catch-at-length is not available, a guesstimate of selectivity needs to be provided. For the latter, stock assessment reports could be a valuable source of information.

4.1.4.1 Catch-at-length files

For the catch at length files, the frequency needs to be specified. The first two columns of the file will be ignored, as it is expected to contain the year and the period (e.g. week, month, quarter). The length class intervals are constructed from the headers of the files, assuming the column name is a numeric value specifying the lower bound of the class intervals. For example, if three columns with headers 10, 15, 20 are provided, the length classes will be [10, 15), [15, 20) and [20, 25).

Note:

Note to Nico: I'm using the average length class to create the upper limit, not Linf as in OSMOSE. This is because too large fish is predicted to be harvested, it can produce a big catch with [20, Linf). Most of the time, [20, 25) is what is really meant to be, so I went for that. Happy to hear your take on the issue, as I also know you have changed the format of the outputs, so this may need to be modified so it remains consistent with OSMOSE.

Within this file, it is assumed the first row matches the first time step. More rows for storing data beyond the model hindcast period (more recent data) is possible, but currently 'older' data should be removed from the file.

```
fisheries.catchatlength.file.sp0 = ../../data/catch_at_length/peru_catchatlength-anchoveta  
fisheries.catchatlength.ndtPerYear.sp0 = 12
```

4.1.4.2 Selectivity

If catch-at-length information is not available, selectivity needs to be specified for every harvested species.

```
fisheries.selectivity.type.sp1 = 3  
fisheries.selectivity.l50.sp1 = 38.2  
fisheries.selectivity.l75.sp1 = 44.7
```

Note that in this case, selectivity for species (spX) is needed, in opposition to selectivity for each fishery (fshX) as for the fisheries parameterization. So, the former is exclusive for the initialization

configuration.

4.2 Model initialization

Once the initialization parameters are defined (cf. [Initialization](#)), the user can run the initialization process.

The first step is to read the configuration file.

```
library(osmose)
library(empirical.selectivity)
library(mgcv)

configDir = file.path("osmose-peru", "osmose-peru_v4.x_develop")
main      = "osmose-peru.R"
simulation = "reference"

configFile = file.path(configDir, main) # path to main configuration file
outputDir  = file.path(configDir, "output", simulation)

conf = read_osmose(input=configFile)
```

The output of the initialization function is an OSMOSE configuration file. The user needs to provide the name of the file. For convenience, I am writing the name of the file already as a `osmose.configuration` key. To keep it simple, we could manually add the name, or directly recommend the user to create the “`osmose.configuration.initialization`”. I was thinking the latter could be simpler.

```
infile = get_par(conf, "osmose.configuration.initialization")

if(is.null(infile)) {
  infile = file.path(configDir, "input", "initial_conditions_test.osm")
}
```

If no `osmose.configuration.initialization` parameter is found (NULL value), then this parameter is created manually.

The initialization itself is performed by the `initialize_osmose` function as follows:

```
out = initialize_osmose(input=configFile, file=inifile, output=outputDir,
                        type = "internannual", osmose = jarFile, version=version,
                        append=FALSE)
```

This function handles the initialization itself. The available initialization methods are:

- `interannual`
- `ncdf`
- `alaia`
- `climatological`

These methods are briefly described below.

4.2.1 interannual method

Here, the objective is to create a text file with the following information:

```
population.initialization.biomass.sp%d
population.initialization.relativebiomass.sp%d
population.initialization.size.sp%d
population.initialization.age.sp%d
population.initialization.nschool.sp%d
population.initialization.tl.sp%d
```

ready to be used by the relative biomass initialization. The difference with the `climatological` method is that the values are calculated using a single species model for each focal species. So, the initialization values are not generated by OSMOSE but we still have something to start with.

TODO

Write the details of the single species model.

4.2.2 ncdf method

When you activate the saving of restarts, as many as replicates will be created. Here, we read all the `ncdf` restart files and take the “mean” of all the state variables, creating a ‘fake’ restart file with the average of all the simulations. All positions are set out of the map ($X=Y=-1$) so reallocation is forced (according to the corresponding maps for the initial time step). A configuration file is created as side effect, indicating the name of the NetCDF initialization file.

4.2.3 climatological method

This method is similar to `ncdf`, but instead of writing a NetCDF file, it creates a text file suitable for the relative biomass initialization method, with the following fields:

```
population.initialization.biomass.sp%d
population.initialization.relativebiomass.sp%d
population.initialization.size.sp%d
population.initialization.age.sp%d
population.initialization.nschool.sp%d
population.initialization.tl.sp%d
```

4.2.4 alaia method

This method replaces the `ncdf` method for Bioen-OSMOSE simulations, for which the average of phenotype does not necessarily make sense. Here, the restart content is copied and the global attribute `step` is set to `-1`, so it can be used as an initialization file by the Osmose model.

Warning:

To explain in a better way `input/init_configuration.osm` is the parameter file for the setup of the initialization `input/peru-initial_conditions.osm` is the output of the initialization setup

Caution!

The `population.initialization.relativebiomass.enabled` parameter must be set to `TRUE`

4.2.5 Running the model

If the initialization runs, that's a success. It is a verbose output, as we are also informing the user of potential problems with the initialization. If successful, go to `input/init_configuration.osm` It is the file where we provide the inputs for the initialization itself, not to be confused with `inifile` where the actual OSMOSE initialization parameters will be created (output). As with any OSMOSE parameters, we can put this on an independent file or just in one big file or splitted in multiple files. OSMOSE (R) will parse the full configuration to search for the appropriate parameters.

The next step is to run the Osmose model by using the `run_model` function:

```
options = "-Xmx3g -Xms1g"
run_osmose(input = configFile, output = outputDir, options = options)

peru = read_osmose(path = outputDir)
```

We can now plot some variables of the initialized simulation:

```
plot(peru, factor=1e-6)
```



```
plot(peru, what="yield", factor=1e-6)
```


All the steps are summarized below:

Figure 4.1: Diagram showing the initialization steps

Chapter 5

Calibration

5.1 Calibration set-up

The Osmose calibration set-up is done by using the `osmose_calibration_setup` function, which setup a new calibration and run some tests.

The current types are:

- `simple`, which uses biomass and landings
- `survey`, which uses the Osmose survey outputs

5.1.1 Calibration initialization

First, a calibration folder needs to be initialized. This is done by a **first** call to the `osmose_calibration_setup` function. For instance, the initialization of a simple calibration is done as follows:

```
jar_file = osmose:::.get_default_osmose_jar()
calibration_path = osmose_calibration_setup(input=configFile,
                                           osmose=jar_file,
                                           type="simple",
                                           name = "my_first_calibration")
```

5.1.1.1 Generated files

This function creates a new folder named after the `name` argument preceded by `calibration_` (`calibration_my_first_calibration` in the above example).

This folder contains the following files:

- `calibration_OMP.pbs`, `calibration_MPI.pbs` and `calibration_sequentiel.pbs` are the PBS script that allows to run the calibration on Datarmor
- `osmose-peru-parguess.osm`, `osmose-peru-parmax.osm`, `osmose-peru-parmin.osm` and `osmose-peru-parphase.osm` are the initial guess, maximum and minimum values of the calibrated parameters and their associated calibration phase (Oliveros-Ramos et al. 2017).
- `osmose-peru-calibration_settings.csv` contains the calibration parameters associates with all the variables used in the calibration.
- The calibration script `.calibration.R`, which is used to run the calibration (see the `calibration_XXX.pbs` files)
- The script that is used to run the Osmose model during the calibration process, `run_model.R`.

Note that the parameters that are needed by Osmose and that are usually calibrated (larval mortalities for instance) will be automatically added in the calibration process. Therefore, they are added in the `osm` files containing the `parguess`, `parmin` and `parmax` parameters.

Note:

The calibration script is hidden. Therefore, it should not be edited manually

TODO

Finish description of the generated files

5.1.1.2 Data templates

The `osmose_calibration_setup` function also creates a folder called `data_templates` in the calibration folder, which contains file templates for calibration data. These files are automatically generated depending on the Osmose configuration that is calibrated. These files will be generated based on:

- The first year of output (`output.start.year` Osmose parameter) and the output frequency (`output.recordfrequency.ndt` parameter)
- The number and names of the focal species
- Whether output surveys (`surveys.enabled.sr1`) are used or not.

In the `osmose-peru` configuration, there are 9 focal species:

```
species.name.sp0 = anchoveta
species.name.sp1 = merluza
species.name.sp2 = sardina
species.name.sp3 = jurel
```

```
species.name.sp4 = caballa
species.name.sp5 = mesopelagicos
species.name.sp6 = munida
species.name.sp7 = pota
species.name.sp8 = euphausidos
```

and three output surveys:

```
surveys.name.sr1 = acousticSurvey
surveys.name.sr2 = trawlSurvey
surveys.name.sr3 = acousticCrustacean
```

Therefore, the `data_templates` will contain the following files

```
peru_biomass.acousticCrustacean-index_month.csv
peru_biomass.acousticSurvey-index_month.csv
peru_biomass-index_month.csv
peru_biomass.trawlSurvey-index_month.csv
peru_yield_month.csv
catch_at_length/peru_catchatlength-anchoveta_month.csv
catch_at_length/peru_catchatlength-caballa_month.csv
catch_at_length/peru_catchatlength-euphausidos_month.csv
catch_at_length/peru_catchatlength-jurel_month.csv
catch_at_length/peru_catchatlength-merluza_year.csv
catch_at_length/peru_catchatlength-mesopelagicos_month.csv
catch_at_length/peru_catchatlength-munida_month.csv
catch_at_length/peru_catchatlength-pota_month.csv
catch_at_length/peru_catchatlength-sardina_month.csv
```

i.e.:

- 1 spatially integrated biomass file (`peru_biomass-index_month.csv`)
- 1 spatially integrated yield biomass file (`peru_yield_month.csv`)
- 1 biomass file for each survey (`peru_biomass.SURVEY-index_month.csv`, with SURVEY the survey name)
- 1 catch-at-length file for each species (`catch_at_length/peru_catchatlength-SPECIES_month.csv` with SPECIES the species name)

The next step for the user is to fill the files in the `data_templates` folder with the calibration data that will be used. **These files need to be filled without modification in their structure.** You can either leave them in the `data_templates` folder, but it is highly suggested to copy the `data_templates` folder in a different location.

Table 5.1: Original calibration settings

variable	type	calibrate	cv	use_data	file	varid	nrows
catchatlength.mesopelagicos	multinom	TRUE	1	TRUE	catch_at_length/peru_catchatlength-mesopelagicos_month.csv	NA	NA
catchatlength.munida	multinom	TRUE	1	TRUE	catch_at_length/peru_catchatlength-munida_month.csv	NA	NA
catchatlength.pota	multinom	TRUE	1	TRUE	catch_at_length/peru_catchatlength-pota_month.csv	NA	NA
catchatlength.euphausidos	multinom	TRUE	1	TRUE	catch_at_length/peru_catchatlength-euphausidos_month.csv	NA	NA

Table 5.2: Corrected calibration settings

variable	type	calibrate	cv	use_data	file	varid	nrows
catchatlength.mesopelagicos	multinom	FALSE	1	TRUE	catch_at_length/peru_catchatlength-mesopelagicos_month.csv	NA	NA
catchatlength.munida	multinom	FALSE	1	TRUE	catch_at_length/peru_catchatlength-munida_month.csv	NA	NA
catchatlength.pota	multinom	FALSE	1	TRUE	catch_at_length/peru_catchatlength-pota_month.csv	NA	NA
catchatlength.euphausidos	multinom	FALSE	1	TRUE	catch_at_length/peru_catchatlength-euphausidos_month.csv	NA	NA

5.1.1.3 Correction of the calibration settings

By default, the `calibration_settings` file will include all the possible variables in the calibration process, based on the output of the Osmose simulation. However, in some cases, Osmose outputs may be missing observational based counterparts.

In this case, the `calibration_settings.csv` file must be manually edited and the `calibrate` column corresponding to the missing data must be set to `FALSE`. And the corresponding data files that were automatically generated in the `data_templates` folder must be removed.

For instance, in the `osmose-peru` configuration, the catch-at-length data for the `mesopelagicos`, `munida`, `pota` and `euphausidos` species are missing. Therefore, the initial calibration settings for these variables (Table 5.1) are corrected as show in Table 5.2.

5.1.2 Calibration finalization

When the observed data have been filled or deleted (in case of missing folder), the `osmose_calibration_setup` function must be called a second time, with the `data_path` argument which specifies where the *real* calibration data are stored.

In the `osmose-peru` case, the `data_templates` files has been copied and pasted in a `real_data` folder. In the latter, the catch-at-length files for the `mesopelagicos`, `munida`, `pota` and `euphausidos` species have been removed and real data has been filled. Therefore, the calibration finalization can be achieved as follows:

```
calibration_path = osmose_calibration_setup(input=configFile,
                                           osmose=jar_file,
                                           type="simple",
```

```
name = "data_templates",  
data_path = "real_data")
```

5.1.2.1 Update

of the `run_model.R` function

At this stage, the user also has the possibility to modify the `run_model.R` function, which makes the connection between *observed* and *simulated* data.

The user is invited to add modification between the `BEGIN USER ADDED` and `END USER ADDED` flags which are located in the `run_model.R` file:

```
### BEGIN USER ADDED  
  
### END USER ADDED
```

Caution!

In most cases, the `run_model.R` script won't need any modification. **Proceed with caution if you do so**

5.1.2.2 Running the calibration

The calibration can be finally run by running the `.calibrate.R`. Since most calibration will be performed on High Performance Calculation (HPC), which are most of the time Linux-based systems, the calibration will be launched as follows:

```
Rscript .calibration.R >>& calibration.log
```

Note:

Datarmor users are invited to run the calibration by using **one** of the `.pbs` scripts generated by the `osmose_calibration_setup` function:

```
qsub calibration_OMP.pbs # Open MP parallelization  
qsub calibration_MPI.pbs # MPI parallelization  
qsub calibration_sequentiel.pbs # No parallelization
```

Chapter 6

References

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